

Evolvability: COMS 4252 Final Project

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Overview

This project examines Leslie Valiant's framework for evolvability, as presented in the Journal of ACM in 2009. It proceeds to address the following questions:

1. What is a high-level description and motivation of evolvability?
2. What are the supporting definitions behind evolvability?
 - How are hypotheses and target functions formed?
 - How is the performance of these functions measured?
3. What is the technical definition of evolvability?
 - How does a p -neighborhood constrain possible hypotheses?
 - How are mutations defined and selected at each generation?
 - How does an evolution sequence proceed over generations?
4. How does evolvability relate to PAC and SQ learnability?
5. What are examples of evolvable and non-evolvable classes?
6. What are the implications of evolvability beyond computational learning theory?

To emphasize what we have learned and how we consider the framework, we will focus as much as possible on further dissecting elements of the framework that are implied but not directly or comprehensively addressed. This includes the independence and dependence of experiences that organisms have, in particular what information is being lost in assuming experiences are independent and how this problem could be solved in a revised framework; analogy of organism evolution in this model to stochastic gradient descent, where each update is not optimal but the overall trend is toward convergence to an ideal given enough resources; and the potential of using this framework to help unite theoretical research in neuroscience and genetics, while considering how it could help advise the general study of the evolution of life across the universe.

1. Evolvability: Introduction

Evolvability is a computational learning model for analyzing the resources needed for certain types of complex systems to emerge. Several functions, sets, and processes are defined for modeling the nature and limits of probabilistic changes in systems that can evolve over time. This includes many-argument boolean functions to abstractly represent a “hypothesis” (*e.g.* actual expression of certain proteins) and an “ideal target” (*e.g.* optimum representation of certain proteins); statistical performance metrics to compare the correlation between the hypothesis and target for sequential inputs of “experiences” at each step of evolution; general and empirical distributions of possible experiences for a system to be tested by, which are sampled with polynomial constraints that mirror those of physical constraints; and bounds for such elements as range of possible mutations per generation, number of generations per population, and size of tolerance for discretizing whether any given mutation is good, neutral, or bad.

We will discuss how each of these elements are defined and organized to form the model for evolvability, which can be used to analyze whether specific classes of functions can be evolved from any given initial hypothesis over some distribution of experiences. The motivation of this model is to enable concrete analysis about a few elements on the evolution of systems: (1) quantifiable limits to the complexity of evolutionary systems as a function of resources such as time, population, possible mutations, and possible hypotheses; and (2) parallel of natural to algorithmic limits, which can enable well-defined proofs from theoretical computer science to deliver new insights for natural scientists and intelligent systems engineers. This new framework ultimately defines evolution as a constrained form of learning.

2. Supporting Definitions of Evolvability

Beneficial Hypotheses and Target Functions. The framework first assumes there is an ideal function f which inputs many variables x_1, \dots, x_n as arguments. For example, the variables may represent the instructions of whether or not to build certain protein sequences from DNA. (Of course, binary activation of phenotype elements can specify entire outcomes as complex as brain and body structure in organisms.) The actual output value of the target function f is arbitrary in our model so long as one direction can be known to be “beneficial” and the other not to be for any given set of inputs. Functions of an organism or population that are beneficial will be defined to be more likely to survive throughout the competitive process of evolution. Systems will pursue this target f for survival through representations r of the same form as f , with input variables x_1, \dots, x_n . Just as what is optimal in any real fitness landscape can change, so too can f be set to change from phase to phase of evolution.

Performance Metrics. We will measure how beneficial any hypothesis representation $r \in R$ is against an ideal $f \in C$ by providing a set of experiences. For each experience

$x^{(i)}$ sets each variable x_1, \dots, x_n to be 1 or 0. Those inputs are computed by $f(x^{(i)})$ and $r(x^{(i)})$ with outputs of 1 or 0, such that if $f(x^{(i)}) = r(x^{(i)})$ then the i th experience is beneficial, otherwise it is not. We provide a total of s experiences $x^{(1)}, \dots, x^{(s)}$ for any given hypothesis r , sampling experiences from the probability distribution D_n over X_n , the set of all possible labelings of x_1, \dots, x_n .

Now we can define a performance metric: $P = \sum_i^s f(x^{(i)})r(x^{(i)})D_n(x^{(i)})$. We see that the value of $f(x^{(i)})$ and $r(x^{(i)})$ at each i will be either 1 or 0, while $D_n(x^{(i)})$ will be the probability of drawing that experience. Therefore performance will be a real value between -1 and 1, from worst to best.

The model will be defined such that representations r with higher performance will be “preferentially selected” (as in the theory of natural selection) to survive and mutate from performing better on future experiences. Closer to observable reality, we further constrain our model to recognize that the set of possible experiences for any given organism is limited to $Y \subseteq X_n$, and the actual distribution D_n is unknown. Then we introduce and use for the remainder of our model the *empirical* performance $P_e = \sum_i^s f(x^{(i)})r(x^{(i)})/s$, where $s = |Y|$ is the number of experiences.

The model is simplified by the definition that draws of Y from D_n are considered to be independent. In reality we expect the experiences that organisms have to often (but not always) depend on previous experiences. For example organisms that perform very well on certain “tasks” are more likely to have future experiences based on these tasks (dependent experience); but sometimes, regardless of all prior experience, an asteroid may suddenly strike and ruin everything (independent experience). Therefore a compelling addition to this model may be allowing for experiences to be partially connected along something like a directed Bayesian network, where conditional probabilities may or may not be incorporated into chains of experiences $x^{(1)}, \dots, x^{(s)}$. This would complicate mapping to previous theoretical computational learning results, but could benefit from introducing results about conditional probability networks, which the experiences of organisms more closely mirrors.

3. Defining Evolvability

A class C of ideal functions f is then loosely considered evolvable if for any f we can start from any representation r_0 and proceed in steps $r_0 \rightarrow r_1 \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow r_g$, such that the performance of r_g on f is at least $1 - \epsilon$. The constraints are that each step of evolution is a result of a single mutation among a reasonably sized (polynomial) population of possible r ; the number of steps g is also limited to a polynomial, reflecting the limited amount of time that the evolution of complex systems has occurred on Earth in; and the number of experiences s used to measure performance of each r must be limited to a polynomial, reflecting the limited lifetime of each organism. We define these concepts more specifically and explain how they interact through the evolutionary process.

p-Neighborhood. We require each $r \in R$ to be polynomial evaluable such that on an experience x we can compute $r(x)$ in polynomial time. For a polynomial $p(n, 1/\epsilon)$, a p -neighborhood includes the set $N(r, \epsilon)$ of size p containing possible $r \in R$ that our r_i may become as r_{i+1} . From N each r may be selected to be r_{i+1} with probability $1/p$. Therefore the role of p -neighborhoods is to constrain the space of mutations at each experience to a polynomial, because the size of the population from which future r are to be selected is necessarily constrained. If desired in the study of genetic evolution, we can estimate empirical values of N for given r by measuring the largest changes in genetic diversity in a population across a defined time step.

Mutation selection. The selection of a new representation r_{i+1} from $N(r_i, \epsilon)$ for each mutation depends on all of the previous parameters (*i.e.* f, p, R, N, D, s, r) along with an additive tolerance parameter t that defines whether or not a given mutation is good, neutral, or bad. The parameter is used to distinguish the performance change between r_i and r_{i+1} . If $P_e(r_{i+1}) > P_e(r_i) + t$, then the mutation is good; else if $-t < P_e(r_{i+1}) - P_e(r_i) < t$, then it is neutral; else it is bad. So performance values of all possible r_{i+1} from $N(r_i, \epsilon)$ are evaluated and each possible r_{i+1} is then allocated into an appropriate set of good, neutral, or bad mutations. The model specifies that at each generational step of selecting which organisms (*i.e.* representations r) survive, if any good mutations have occurred then one of them is chosen, else a neutral mutation is chosen. This is a way of simulating the advantage the mutation is defined to give. Bad mutations will never be chosen because those organisms that did not mutate will be preferred over those with bad mutations. So we define the original value r_i to also be in $N(r_i, \epsilon)$, and thus in the set of neutral mutations, so it can be a default value for r_{i+1} .

The choice of r_{i+1} is selected over the uniform distribution of the set of good or neutral mutations. This interesting constraint suggests that even if an organism or population could possibly have a mutation that it could suddenly achieve a much higher performance through, the probability will not favor this representation being selected if several other mutations are also good; therefore this model asserts that each step of evolution will not be a perfect optimization, but more like the process known as stochastic gradient descent. So while the best mutation in the p -neighborhood is not necessarily selected, it is expected that over a large number of steps the representations will slowly converge to f .

The model requires that *any* representation r_0 can ultimately reach an evolvable f ; this is a more flexible condition than requiring that only a certain “initialized” $r^* = r_0$ can proceed to f . To strictly enforce this, we bound the tolerance parameter to be larger than ℓ and smaller than u , where ℓ and u are polynomials related by $u^n \leq \ell \leq u$ for some choice of n . The logic behind bounding our tolerance in this way is to prevent some system from resetting to a particular r^* in the first step. It could do this technically if the tolerance is very large and r^* is in N , such that in one step r_0 may

change to $r_{i+1} = r^*$ that may technically be considered neutral but, in terms of actual performance, is significantly worse. The idea is then that this “backdoor initialization” is prevented by preventing the tolerance from being set too large by our theoretical mischievous initializing agent. Based on this justification alone, this may be an unnecessary constraint because even if r^* is in N (which, if r^* is very different from r_0 , it should not be selectable within a single mutation) then r^* still can only be selected over the uniform probability distribution with probability $1/p$. However we will show that bounding the tolerance is useful when done so as a function of n and ϵ , and it can introduce an additional stochastic layer into the optimization.

Generations. Within polynomial bounds on the tolerance we may randomly select the tolerance at each generation. This means, for example, that what is considered a good mutation at one step may be neutral at another and then good again later, all with the same absolute values of performance. In order to guarantee that the model converges to a performance less than $1 - \epsilon$ with probability greater than $1 - \epsilon$, it becomes necessary to bound the number of experiences s and number of generations g by making them both polynomial functions of n and $1/\epsilon$. By specifying the polynomials that bound our tolerance to be $\ell(1/n, \epsilon)$ and $u(1/n, \epsilon)$ our tolerances will decrease as ϵ increases; this is an important way of ensuring that small incremental steps of $O(\epsilon)$ can be made in the region where r_i is close to f .

Then we formally define that C is (ℓ, u) -evolvable over D if it follows $r_0 \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow r_g$ given $(p, s, \ell, u, R, N, g, D, \epsilon, n)$ where the performance of r_g is at least $1 - \epsilon$ with probability $1 - \epsilon$ for any $f \in C$, any $r_0 \in R$, any $0 < \epsilon < 1$. A class C that is (ℓ, u) -evolvable over some D , for polynomials ℓ, u, p, s, n, N , is simply considered evolvable.

4. Evolvability Relation to PAC and SQ Learning

Classes that are evolvable according to the previous definitions can be shown to be a subset of those that are learnable according to the probably approximately correct (PAC) and statistical query (SQ) models as follows.

Evolvability \subseteq PAC Learnability. When evolution proceeds at each step to collect $s(n, 1/\epsilon)$ experiences and then tests its current hypothesis by measuring the performance P_e , this is equivalent to taking a single instance in PAC learning with a labeled example and testing to see if the hypothesis agrees or not with the target concept. Just as in PAC learning the evolvable algorithm will then update its hypothesis in polynomial time. Each time the hypothesis is tested it is equivalent in the PAC learning model to checking if a certain accuracy threshold has been met. After polynomial number of updates, the final hypothesis is correct on at least $1 - \epsilon$ of examples from D , with probability $1 - \epsilon$, just as required by a PAC learning algorithm.

Evolvability \subseteq SQ Learnability. To run a SQ algorithm from an evolvable one, we only need to simulate the set of mutations that are good and neutral. This can be done by

examining all possible r_{i+1} in the p -neighborhood for r_i and asking the oracle what the probability is for each that r_i and r_{i+1} are equal to f . Specifically we need to know $\Pr[r_i = r_{i+1} = f]$, $\Pr[r_i = f, r_{i+1} \neq f]$, $\Pr[r_i \neq f, r_{i+1} = f]$, and $\Pr[r_i \neq f, r_{i+1} \neq f]$. With these probabilities we can then assign each r_{i+1} into a category of neutral if $\Pr[r_i = r_{i+1} = f]$ or $\Pr[r_i \neq f, r_{i+1} \neq f]$ are greater than $\Pr[r_i = f, r_{i+1} \neq f]$ and $\Pr[r_i \neq f, r_{i+1} = f]$; good if $\Pr[r_i \neq f, r_{i+1} = f]$ is greater than all the others; and bad if $\Pr[r_i = f, r_{i+1} \neq f]$ is greater than all the others. This simulation can be done by requesting an expected number of experiences that is a polynomial in $(n, 1/\epsilon)$ for each possible hypothesis. So this is a polynomial multiplied by a polynomial is still a polynomial, and therefore we have an efficient SQ algorithm.

We therefore conclude that $\text{Evolvability} \subseteq \text{SQ Learnability} \subseteq \text{PAC Learnability}$.

5. Examples of Evolvable and Non-Evolvable Classes

Non-evolvable classes. We see that evolvability necessarily implies learnability, but the reverse is not true. The class of parity functions, for example, have been shown to be not efficiently learnable in the SQ model using any representation. Therefore there is no biological function that can be expected to behave like a parity function. Another class of functions that is known to be not evolvable, because it is known to be not learnable, is boolean threshold functions, unless $\text{NP}=\text{RP}$. This is one of the beautiful results of the evolvable model: any class known to be not learnable is known to be not evolvable. Beyond this, one unique constraint on evolvable models that will prevent evolvability is when there is no way to test a polynomial number of hypotheses in a neighborhood while guaranteeing convergence to a performance. Prior results from learning theory also indicate that a system cannot evolve when the number of experiences is greater than its complexity; and if some step or computation in processing evolvability implies solving a problem believed to be computationally hard, then the concept class can be believed to not be evolvable.

Evolvable classes. Monotone conjunctions and disjunctions are classes that are evolvable over the uniform distribution. We do not cover all of the details of the proof here, but understand that its components include the following: adding and removing literals from the representation class to build a p -neighborhood that lower bounds performance gain of each mutation; showing how tolerances t and experience size s that are functions of n and ϵ can guarantee that performance-improving mutations are correctly identified with high probability; running the algorithm over $g(n, 1/\epsilon)$ generations with up to $p(n, 1/\epsilon)$ mutations per generation to be tested, while constraining the probability of failure to properly allocate each mutation in the sets good or neutral for each test of mutation. The bulk of the proof then follows in work on proving several modular claims showing effects on performance of adding and removing literals from the ideal and representation classes. These claims are organized to upper bound the probability of error over the possible values of the size of the conjunction to be evolved,

relative the number of conjunctions in our representational class. This ultimately leads to the result that conjunctions can be evolved within a number of generations $g(n, 1/\epsilon)$ that is of the order $O(n \log(n/\epsilon))$. The same result follows for disjunctions by switching operators for AND and OR while negating inputs.

These are only a few examples of concept classes that are and are not evolvable. There is significant opportunity to explore how other concept classes fit into this framework.

6. Implications of Evolvability

Evolvability is a model based on polynomial constraints on the complexity of systems that can emerge from step-by-step mutations as functions of time, population, and space of possible representations available at each step.

By seeing mathematically from these structures that evolvability can be considered as a subset of learnability, we are afforded with new ways of attacking complex problems such as understanding manifestations of genetic learning and neural learning in terms of organism function. The premise is that in theory we should be able to map out how complex behaviors can be represented as functions of experience coherently defined across long and short timescales of genetic evolution and brain learning. Any realistic framework for unifying how genes and brains learn needs to probably incorporate the conditional probabilities that are assigned to learning capacity of brains as a function of what has been genetically learned. This makes the previous aside discussed about Bayesian networks all the more interesting and relevant.

If evolvability is useful for analyzing evolution on Earth, because of its general definitions, it may also be useful to scientists seeking to model the complexity of systems that can evolve naturally throughout the universe. NASA and NSF invest in research on modeling the possible complexity of chemical systems that may emerge from diverse physical environments, including in the solar system to advise future exploration. The evolvability framework can increase clarity on how to probabilistically model evolution in new environments given known physical resource limits about them.

As a matter of communicating and applying the results of this work, scientists outside of computational learning theory could use examples of how concept classes of functions may be manifested in physical systems. Such mappings across computational theory and physical systems are not only wonderful but possibly essential to breakthroughs in complex research areas such as in health care. There will be enormous demand and opportunity over the coming decades for such mappings, as the role of learning for evolutionary intelligence is increasingly understood and developed.